

FOOTBALL AS A BASIC TOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of the volume of educational and scientific information in the conditions of developing scientific and technological progress inevitably leads to a change in the educational and training process. The main thing is the change of training sessions, the versatile development of technical preparedness, replenishment of the fund of motor skills and abilities. It is known that the technical readiness of football players is one of the most important factors on which the activity and effectiveness of team, group and individual actions depend.

In the context of the reform of Uzbekistan, the issues of strengthening the physical and spiritual health of a person, the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the realization of human individuality, which are considered as criteria for social progress, are of particular importance. During the period of study in higher educational institutions, the abilities and inclinations of students are revealed, the most active development of moral and aesthetic qualities takes place, the formation and stabilization of character, interests, psychomotor functions. All this emphasizes, on the one hand, the presence of high potential opportunities of students, and on the other hand, the need to maximize the realization of these opportunities in the learning process [1, 2]. The problem of improving physical education at the university has long been

the subject of study by many specialists who pay increasing attention to the student's personality to engage in one or another type of his sports activity.

Physical education is built in such a way as to ensure the maximum professional effect in fostering entrepreneurship, originality of thinking, perseverance, ambition, and the ability to take risks. At the same time, sports and physical education activities are one of the forms of self-expression and self-affirmation of the student, determining his lifestyle, general cultural and socially significant priorities. It is known that the desire for success is brought to the fore in sports, the desire of the individual to realize his capabilities within a certain sports scenario is encouraged. The result of the combined educational and sports activities of students is the formation of socially significant qualities: social activity,

independence, self-confidence, as well as ambition.

In our opinion, in a technical university (with a predominant number of male content), the sports specialization "football" is of the greatest interest. The analysis of scientific and methodological literature has shown many different programs for the use of football in physical education of students.

But the issues of teaching students of technical universities with poor training in sports, in particular, in football, remain insufficiently studied. The study of this problem is very important, since football is very popular among students and is one of the necessary means of physical training, strengthening and maintaining the health of students in the process of physical education at the university.

At the same time, in order to improve the educational process, pedagogical efforts should be aimed at bringing the subjective desires and goals of students closer to the objectively set tasks of physical education at the university [7].

The solution to the above problem, according to V. A. Ermakov, is based on the liberalization of the educational process, which contributes to the inclusion of a variety of different types of physical culture and sports activities. The author believes that this approach will lead to the creation of as many alternative physical education programs as possible.

The purpose of this work was to develop the physical and technical-tactical readiness of students of the specialization "football" as one of the basic means of physical education. It is known that the physical fitness of students who have chosen this specialization is one of the most important factors on which the

activity and effectiveness of team, group and individual technical and tactical actions depend. No matter how technical and tactically competent a "football player" is, he will never achieve success without good and versatile physical fitness. A team in which the physical fitness of even one player will not be adequate will not succeed either. Therefore, physical education teachers have always had and will always have two questions: 1) which manifestations of physical performance are the most important for football? 2) what exercises and what methods they need to be developed and improved so that not just endurance, speed or strength grow, but all these physical qualities within the framework of technical and tactical actions. The curriculum of the university of specialization "football" provides for the development of basic physical qualities: endurance, strength, flexibility, speed and strength training.

In this regard, the question arises about the limits of functionality and methods of monitoring students in order to differentiate the load and determine the effectiveness of classes with students. At the same time, for students who have chosen the sports specialization "football", it is necessary to study technical readiness. At the preliminary stage of experimental work, a study of physical fitness and working capacity was conducted among 120 first-year students of the sports specialization "football". Dynamic assessment of physical, technical readiness and working capacity of the students was carried out twice in the academic year, control tests to identify endurance were: running 1000 meters in September and 2000 meters in April; speed-strength endurance was detected by jumping from a

place in September and May; speed was detected by running 100 meters in September and May; strength fitness by the number of pull-ups on the crossbar in September and May.

Methods and organization of research. To identify indicators of physical and technical fitness, traditional research methods used: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, questionnaires, pedagogical observation. Without touching on the results of the ascertaining experiment in this article, we will focus on the assessment of physical fitness. Traditional tests were adopted: running 100 m; 1000 m; pull-up; jumping into a mine from a place. To assess technical readiness, tests such as precision strikes from 16 meters (five strikes indicating the sides) were used — the number of hits was taken into account; driving the ball with the outline of the racks (1 m, for a time); juggling the ball on the spot alternately with the right and left foot (number of times).

Results and their discussion. The students chose the specialization "football", as they were interested in it before. So, out of 120 respondents, 30% were engaged in football in sports schools, the rest - either in a secondary school or in courtyards. Football experience averaged 4 years. The number of students with a sports category in football was 25,96. At the same time, the majority of respondents would like to improve their technical and tactical abilities. At the same time, 70% of all respondents rate physical fitness as unsatisfactory and believe that two classes a week according to the academic schedule is not enough.

However, the majority (87 96) of 2nd year students believe that in one academic year they have achieved a lot, that is, they have

learned such techniques as: passing the ball, accurate shots on goal, driving and possession of the ball.

So, at the preliminary stage of experimental work, a study was conducted of the technical readiness of students of the first and second courses of study, sports specialization "football".

The results were as follows in the control group: precision strikes — 2 hits, ball driving - 4.9 seconds, juggling - 22 times. In the experimental group, an increase in indicators for similar tests was revealed. So, driving the ball — 4.3 seconds, juggling - 32 times, strikes for accuracy - 7 hits.

It should be noted that the physical fitness of the students of the experimental group was higher compared to the control group. On average, the dynamics of the indicators was as follows: running for 1000 meters - the result is 3.50 minutes; for 2000 meters - 9.13 minutes; for 100 meters in September - 14.0 seconds, in May - 13.8 seconds; the number of pull-ups on the crossbar in September was 8 times, and in May 10 times; the long jump from a place was 222 centimeters, and in May - 226 centimeters. Performance test PWC170 significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased from 850 ± 45 KGM/min to 1020 KGM/min ($P < 0.05$).

Positive dynamics of physical qualities of evidence reserves the reserve capacity of the organism of students involved in the specialization of "football," a study of physical performance allows a differentiated approach to the methodology of conducting classes with the aim of improving functionality involved.

The use of the sports specialization "football" in the physical education of

students of a technical university indicates that playing and training activities have a complex and versatile effect on the body of those involved, develops basic physical qualities - speed, agility, endurance, strength, increase functionality, form various motor skills necessary in future professional activity. Year-round football classes in Siberia contribute to physical hardening and increased motor activity.

The inclusion of the sports specialization "football" in the educational process of physical education of students contributes to the improvement of the adaptive capabilities of the body involved, which manifests itself in increasing physical fitness, endurance and reducing the incidence of colds. Thanks to a variety of motor activity and improvement of coordination abilities, football students are faster and more successful they master it vitally.

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